

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF BETWEEN ARABIC AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGE GRAMMATICAL GENDER IN LINGUISTICS

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this article is to present the similarities and differences in gender and nouns between Russian and Arabic language. As it is known that in learning Arabic there are many mistakes which occur as a result of the interference of the mother tongue especially on grammar level. To overcome this problem contrastive analysis is used to show the similarities and differences. The method which the researcher used analyze the sentences structure. The main findings are that both languages have gender and number system.

Introduction

Gender is a grammatical feature, in a family with person, number, and case. In the languages that have grammatical gender - according to a representative typological sample, almost half of the languages in the world - it is a property that separates nouns into classes. These classes are often meaningful and often linked to biological sex, which is why many languages are said to have a "masculine" and a "feminine" gender. However, gender systems may be based on other semantic distinctions or may reflect formal properties of the noun. In all cases, the defining property is agreement: the behavior of associated words. Gender systems vary greatly in the languages of the world. They differ in the number of classes, the basic rules of assignment, and how and where the genders are marked. Because of the deterministic nature of agreement, gender is generally absent in isolated languages and in young languages such as sign languages where morphology is largely unconstrained. Gender is therefore seen as a mature phenomenon in language.

All Arabic nouns have a gender associated with them. It is important to know this gender because the remaining elements in the Arabic sentence like the verbs and adjectives. Have the same gender. Arabic nouns are masculine unless they are proven to be feminine. Gender plays a very important role in Arabic grammar and a lot of rules.

In Arabic there are two types of nouns in terms of gender:

1. Masculine المذكر

2. Feminine المونث

There is no special sign for identifying masculine words, and words should be assumed to be

masculine المذكر unless they belong to one of the following categories:

1. Real feminine (feminine by meaning) 2. Conventional feminine

Real feminine (feminine by meaning)

Conventional feminine

Conventional feminine indicating nouns of things not truly feminine but follow a conventional rule. It includes the following :

Nouns ending with taa marbootah (ة) it is considered as the basic feminine sign.

The letter (ة) is also added to masculine nouns or adjectives to make them feminine

Names of towns and, cities and countries, parts of body that are in pairs:

Words used by Arabs as feminine without any rule or reason. They are: sky, hell, bucket, fire, war, well, sun, house, wind, soul, earth. If a noun is feminine then the verbs, adjectives etc. must also be feminine. These are exceptions that used by Arabs as feminine. There is no rule or reason to explain why the moon is masculine.

Feminine	Masculine
This car is beautiful- هَذِهِ السَّيَّارَةُ جَمِيلَةٌ	This house is beautiful- هَذَا الْبَيْتُ جَمِيلٌ
Maryam is a hardworking student- مَرْيَمُ طَالِبَةٌ مُجْتَهِدَةٌ	Talha is a hardworking student- تَالْحَةُ طَالِبٌ مُجْتَهِدٌ
Egypt is very big and beautiful- مِصْرٌ كَبِيرَةٌ وَ جَمِيلَةٌ جَدًّا	Egypt is very big and beautiful country -مِصْرُ بَلَدٌ كَبِيرٌ وَ جَمِيلٌ جَدًّا

In Russian language there are three types of nouns in terms of grammatical gender. They are:

1. Masculine он - he noun ends with –a consonant –ь (soft sign)
2. Feminine она - she noun ends with –a/я –ь (soft sign)
3. Neuter оно - it noun ends with o/e

As we know Russian language has three grammatical genders: masculine, feminine and

neuter. Gender agreements are expressed as suffixes and appear in singular adjectives, past tense verbs, demonstrative pronouns, participles, and certain pronouns.

The gender of animate nouns usually matches their meaning. For example:

студент - (male) student

студентка - (female) student

папа - father

мама - mother

дедушка - grandfather

бабушка - grandmother

The gender of the inanimate nouns is not tied to the noun meaning.

газета -feminine. There is nothing feminine about a newspaper. We know and can tell the gender of a noun by looking at its last letter in the nominative singular form. The words that are borrowed from other languages for example:

кофе - masculine

кенгуру - masculine

такси - neuter

меню - neuter

Common gender examples:

копуша - slowpoke

коллега - colleague

непоседа - restless/spaz

It will be important to mention grammatical gender in job titles. Some masculine nouns can be used for both males and females. For example:

врач - doctor

водитель - driver

дизайнер - designer

президент - president

As you see they all end with a consonant letter, so that means that they all are masculine and there are some other nouns that can have both feminine and masculine versions. Those nouns can have both feminine masculine endings. For example: **Pairs of masculine and feminine nouns:**

учитель - male/female teacher

учительница - only female teacher

стюард - male flight attendant

стюардесса - female flight attendant

писатель - male writer

писательница - female writer

поэт - male/female poet

поэтесса - female poet

In Russian, nouns are assigned a gender based on their gender. Russian nouns have three genders: male, female, and neuter. It is generally possible to determine the grammatical gender of a noun based on its ending, which is usually the same as the biological gender of its referents in dictionaries. However, they can be different, such as nouns denoting occupations and nouns of common gender. The grammatical gender of Russian nouns is expressed not in the plural, but in the singular in various cases, and determines the past tense endings of adjectives, pronouns, adjective-like words, and verbs in sentences. In this article, we proposed a psychological method to study the effect of Russian grammatical gender on Russian speakers in a classification task. The experiment focuses on comparing different image grouping policies for Russian and Uzbek speakers, and the language has no grammatical gender. We found evidence for the influence of Russian grammatical gender on Russian-speaker cognition, and this result was supported by statistical analyses. Furthermore, the impact of bilingualism on speaker cognition has been pointed out, which will be an interesting topic for future research on the language relativity hypothesis.

We have seen that the grammatical gender of nouns may be determined either by semantic or non semantic means, and that other elements in a phrase or clause agree in gender with the nouns. In Russian, many animate nouns that are grammatically one gender may refer to either men or women. Some of these nouns are hybrid nouns, meaning that some elements may agree with the gender of the referent instead of the grammatical gender of the noun, producing mixed agreement.

Gender interacts with other grammatical features in different ways. For example, you can limit it to singular or third person and cut it case-sensitively. These and other interrelationships can complicate the task of identifying gender systems in first or second language acquisition. But children learn gender early on and use different cues. In contrast, gender is notoriously difficult for second language learners. This is especially true for adults and learners who do not have a gender system in their native language. Nevertheless, tests show that native language proficiency can be achieved even in this group. The relationship between grammatical gender and object is arbitrary for inanimate objects. The word "chair" is masculine, but the word "table" is feminine. When an Arabic learner learns a new word, it is critical to understand the gender associated with that word. The word "moon" is masculine, while "sun" is feminine. Adjectives must have the same gender of the nouns they describe, e.g. "new employee" can be either (جديد موظف) masculine, or (جديدة موظفة) feminine. Both the noun and the adjective must have the same gender. Likewise, gender of words referring to inanimate objects must agree with the gender of adjectives used to describe them, e.g. (كرسي قديم) "an old chair" both the noun and adjective are masculine, and (طاولة قديمة) "an old table" both the noun and adjective are feminine.;

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